

D7.1

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

BIOSCHAMP Project

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Executive Summary

This document is the “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan” of the BIOSCHAMP Project, which is the **Deliverable 7.1 of the Work Package 7** (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation) of the Grant Agreement 101000651. This plan further develops the points included in the “Preliminary plan for the dissemination of project results” included in the Grant Agreement (Part B, Section 2.2).

The **main objective** of this plan (CD&E Plan, from here onwards) is to provide all project partners with an outline that covers: (1) the main messages of the project, (2) the target groups the project seeks to impact, (3) the actions to be carried out to reach them and (4) the general and specific obligations regarding Dissemination and Communication of the project that all partners must be aware of.

(1) (2) Key target groups for the project are the mushroom industry (mushroom associations, mushroom growers, and raw material providers) researchers active in mushroom cultivation, policy makers, “Sustainability Networks” and general public. “Sustainability Networks” are networks or organisations in the mushroom sector dedicated to sustainability in agriculture and environmental protection through which it will be possible to reach a broader spectrum of relevant stakeholders. Apart from the **generic messages**, each target group counts with its own **tailored messages**.

(3) The Dissemination and Communication actions are part of an online and offline strategy that includes: press releases; a project webpage; social media accounts; production of promotional materials (flyers, roll-up and technical infographics); 12 practice abstracts; 7 technical magazines and peer reviewed publications; industry events; scientific conferences; a newsletter targeted to industry agents and potential agents, networking activities with “Sustainability networks” and invitations to policy makers to better know and support the project.

(4) Obligations related to Communication & Dissemination cover visibility of funding, the figure of the Communications Representative, notifications, minimum communication actions expected of each partner and basic visual guidelines. Regarding knowledge management and ethics, this document offers a broad overview of the main points to consider and refers to the specific deliverables that tackle this topic.

To sum up, this document describes and presents the most relevant aspects of the Communication and Dissemination strategy of the BIOSCHAMP project, establishes responsibilities and timings, and includes practical examples for the different cases. It is divided in eight sections plus the annexes. As the project develops, this document will be updated in future Deliverables (D7.4 and D7.8).

1 Introduction

This document describes the project's Dissemination and Communication Plan and the actions that will be carried out for the achievement of the objectives raised. The document has been conceived and prepared by INNOVARUM (the commercial brand of EURIZON S.L., partner 7) and Work Package 7 leader (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation). INNOVARUM will oversee the implementation, coordination and execution of the actions included in this document.

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CD&E Plan, from now on) is the Deliverable 7.1 of the BIOSCHAMP Project (WP7). This Deliverable is made of two parallel documents: (1) The CD&E Plan (this document) and (2) an Excel file with a sample structure for tracking progress on all actions included in the CD&E Plan. Future deliverables that will evaluate and update the content of these documents are:

- 7.4. Update of the D&C actions - Update to the D&C plan submitted as deliverable 7.1 (Due for Month 21)
- 7.8. Summary of the D&C actions - Report reflecting all the D&C actions that have been undertaken in the project (due for Month 42).

These three deliverables (7.1, 7.4 and 7.8) will be open to the public.

1.1 Scope of the document

The CD&E Plan is the core document outlining the project's dissemination and communication activities. This plan is fundamental for a good coordination of all initiatives, defining the correct content of the messages, which should be adapted to each of the targeted audiences, getting the required CD&E impact and effectively communicating the project results. Effective communication will encourage interested stakeholders to actively participate in the project and enhance the visibility of its results.

This Dissemination and Communication Plan includes:

- An overview of the Work Package 7 and of its tasks.
- The basic structure of the communication strategy: Internal & external communication.
- An outline of the main objectives of the Dissemination and Communication Plan.
- The target groups the CD&E Plan aims to reach to achieve its objectives.
- The actions to specifically reach the defined target groups.
- General and specific Partners' obligations regarding Dissemination and Communication.
- Dissemination, Knowledge Management and Open Access to data that it is produced throughout the development of the project.
- Compliance of ethics requirement in communication and dissemination activities.

2 The Work Package 7 and relevant tasks

The Work Package 7 is divided in 5 Tasks. From them, Tasks which focus on Dissemination & Communication activities include Task 7.4 and 7.5 (defined in more detail in the table). These are the main tasks this Plan will develop and work on.

Table 1: Tasks within WP7

Type	Title	Coordination	Support-participation	Target	Duration
Task	Task 7.1: Commercialisation plan	KBVB	INNOVARUM		M28-M42
Task	Task 7.2: Route to EU supply chain establishment	NEWFOSS	WR, KBVB		M28-M42
Task	Task 7.3: Study of patent options and innovation management	CTICH	UOXF, KBVB, NEWFOSS and INNOVARUM		M1-M42
M1Task	Task 7.4: Dissemination activities M1-M42	INNOVARUM	CTICH		M1-M42
Action	Project website (T7.4) M6	INNOVARUM	Partners when contacted	200 monthly visits	
Action	Social media Twitter (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners: dissemination	600 followers	
Action	Social media LinkedIn (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners: dissemination	300 followers	
Action	Publications in peer-reviewed journals and industry magazines (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners	7 publications	
Action	BIOSCHAMP practice abstracts (T7.4)	CTICH	Partners contacted	12	
Action	Promo materials: roll ups (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners: dissemination	4 designs	
Action	Promo materials: flyers (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners: dissemination	500 prints	
Action	Promo materials: technical infographic (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners: dissemination	100 prints	
Action	Promo materials downloads total (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners: dissemination	200 downloads	
Action	Industry events (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners	12	
Action	Scientific conferences (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners	3 major conferences	
Action	Networking: project page in relevant networks websites or through proof of collaboration framework (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners	10	
Action	Targeted invitations to reach out to experts/ political figures/ authorities on regional, national and EU levels (T7.4)	INNOVARUM	All partners	12	
Action	Final event organised in Spain (T7.4)	CTICH	All partners	75 participants	
Task	Task 7.5: Communication activities M1-M42	INNOVARUM	CTICH		M1-M42
Action	Short video (T7.5)	INNOVARUM	All partners: dissemination	300 views by year 3	
Action	Long video (T7.5)	INNOVARUM	All partners: dissemination	300 views by year 3	
Action	Press releases (T7.5)	INNOVARUM	All partners: dissemination	5	

2.1 Objectives of the CD&E Plan

The main objectives of the BIOSCHAMP Dissemination and Communication Plan are:

- 1- Develop a comprehensive communication strategy: provide effective tools, messages, and methods for communication.
- 2- Identify target audiences and stakeholders that can benefit from the results produced by BIOSCHAMP project and maximise the impact of the innovations developed. Disseminate BIOSCHAMP project results among potential customers, fostering the development of new market opportunities.
- 3- Review and describe the specific actions that will support the communication strategy, its target audiences, and its KPIs.
- 4- Define strategies to extend the communities reached during the implementation of the project and after its completion. This will be done through the define actions to contribute to the knowledge base for shaping the policy within the matter of biostimulants and peatland protection, supporting sustainability of the mushroom sector.
- 5- Include relevant information regarding Open Data and good Dissemination practices, to assure that the range of materials developed is accessible through dissemination infrastructures which are sustainably functioning beyond the lifetime of the project.

3 Internal and external communication

3.1 Internal communication actions

The internal communication actions seek the effective communication among participants within the project. CTICH, as Project Coordinator will oversee the internal communication of the project with the support from INNOVARUM, Communication Partner and Work Package 7 leader (WP7).

Some examples of what this type of actions involves are:

1. Elaboration of a Dissemination and Communication Plan for all partners to follow and use as reference. (D7.1 of the WP7)
2. Collaboration and information exchange between project partners and with the EU Commission.
3. Storage and organisation of all information exchanged.
4. Facilitation of project related information to all partners to improve decision making processes.
5. Encouragement to project partners to distribute the information generated during activities' execution.

3.1.1 Specific tools for Internal Communication

Specific tools for internal communication include:

- 1- **Consortium face-to-face meetings:** Ordinary meetings and Extraordinary meetings if needed.
- 2- **Mailing list for effective communication:**
 - A general mailing lists with all partners for general project matters.
 - A communication mailing list that only includes Communication Coordinators.
 - An ethics mailing list, including ethics responsible, to comply with the European Commission's ethic requirements.
 - An Executive Board mailing list, with the leaders of all Work Packages.
- 3- **Email, phone calls and video calls.**
- 4- **Microsoft TEAMS** will be the main tool for the internal communication of the project. All relevant documents, dissemination materials, templates... etc will be updated and uploaded into this platform. The platform will be handled by the Project Coordinator (CTICH).
TEAMS will also be available for all partners to use in case they need it to organise a meeting with an organisation outside the consortium.

3.2 External communication actions

External Communications include those actions targeted to people or entities in the project's external environment. External Communication makes the most of the actions covered in relevant communication & dissemination actions in the WP7 of the Grant Agreement: Task 7.4 (Dissemination activities) and 7.5 (Communication activities) - efficient internal communication will still be transversal to all of them).

4 General messages

4.1 What is BIOSCHAMP?

The BIOSCHAMP project aims to develop an integrated approach to tackle the mushroom cultivation challenges: an alternative and sustainable peat-free biostimulant casing for the mushroom industry, reducing the dependency on and need for pesticides and contributing to improve the productivity, the sustainability, and the profitability of the European mushroom sector.

4.1.1 Problems that make BIOSCHAMP necessary

The mushroom sector in Europe is facing various challenges that make BIOSCHAMP necessary:

1. The mushroom sector is heavily affected by diseases: currently mycoparasites are responsible for the largest crop losses in commercial mushroom production.
2. There are no adequate means of controlling diseases: many growers struggle to find methods.
3. Dependency of chemical products (pesticides) to prevent disease outbreaks.
4. The number of allowed chemical products (fungicides) to treat mushroom diseases is decreasing and resistant strains have been reported – there are fewer specific tools to fight the problem!
5. The EU needs to accelerate the transition towards a pesticide-free mushroom sector.

4.1.2 The Solution BIOSCHAMP offers

BIOSCHAMP offers the following solutions to the challenges the mushroom sector faces in Europe:

- BIOSCHAMP will develop a peat-free casing soil to serve as a carrier for selected microbiota (bacterial strains) that will act as crop biostimulants. This solution will also be an alternative to pesticides, contributing to improve the productivity, the sustainability, and the profitability of the European mushroom sector.
- BIOSCHAMP will further facilitate circularity and resource efficiency in the mushroom sector. The biostimulant peat-free casing soil that BIOSCHAMP will develop will also integrate NF Fibres (based on biomass from agricultural residual waste streams) and spent casing (recycled from mushroom cultivation).

The solution will be tested at four mushroom farms across the EU which integrate all the European cropping systems. This will be an integrated solution that combines two 100% bio-based, renewable, and synergistic components.

4.2 What are the objectives of the project?

The goal of the BIOSCHAMP project is to improve the mushroom sector industrial profitability while reducing the agronomical need for pesticides by 90 %. This will help mushroom growers meet consumer demands to find alternatives to fungicide dependence.

4.3 Which partners integrate the BIOSCHAMP PROJECT?

BIOSCHAMP is coordinated by one of the Spanish Association of Mushroom Growers (ASOCHAMP). CTICH will work for 3.5 years together with research institutions - Inagro vzw (BE), Wageningen Research (NL), CSIC, University of Oxford (UK) -, key suppliers of the mushroom industry- KBVB (NL), world leader in providing substrate (casing) to mushroom growers and FERTINAGRO, large company specialised in fertilisers & plant

protection products-, 1 large mushroom producer –EUROCHAMP (ES), –small mushroom producers - conventional UGLK (PL), organic EKOFUNGI (RS) and grass fiber producer NF Fibre B.V. (NL) – and an innovation organisation active in the bioeconomy – INNOVARUM (ES).

4.3.1 How long will the project last?

The project will last 3.5 years. It started in October 2020 and will end in March 2024.

4.4 Tone of the messages

The tone of all BIOSCHAMP-related communication will be informative, descriptive, and positive, showing a clear focus on achieving the expected impacts and communicating them efficiently. The tone used in each communication activity will be adapted to the specific target audience.

5 Target Audiences & specific messages

BIOSCHAMP CD&E plan will differentiate between **4 main stakeholder groups** (industry, researchers, policy makers and sustainability networks) and **fifth group composed of general audiences** (citizens, children, professionals with not technical background...).

5.1.1 Target audience 1: Mushroom industry

Industry audiences cover:

- **Mushroom producer associations.** Producer associations bring together individual mushroom producers, targeting them allows for a straightforward strategy to reach a bigger number of individual producers through an efficient set of actions.

For example, a key producer association within the consortium is ASOCHAMP: Professional Association of Substrate and Mushroom Producers, a non-lucrative association, gathering most mushroom growers, compost plants and related industries, within their facilities. ASOCHAMP fosters within its facilities the technical research organisation CTICH – BIOSCHAMP project coordinator.

Other relevant mushroom associations outside the consortium the BIOSCHAMP project will target include:¹

Table 2: relevant mushroom producers associations in Europe

Association	Country	Contact email	Link
REO Veiling	Belgium	info@reo.be	https://www.reo.be/en/home
Dansk Champignon Dyrker Ferening, Hedebovej 47	Denmark	egehøj@egehøj.dk	http://www.egehøj-champignon.dk/
MAGOTE Hungarian Mushroom Growers' Association	Hungary	info@magote.hu	http://www.magote.hu/en/
Associazione Italiana Fungicoltori	Italy	info@fun.go.it	http://www.fun.go.it/
SBGU – STOWARZYSZENIE BRAN_Y GRZYBÓW UPRAWNYCH	Poland	sbgu@sbgu.com.pl	http://www.sbgu.com.pl/
ANICC: Association nationale interprofessionnelle du champignon de couche	France	contact@anicc.com	http://www.champignonidee.fr
FNSACC: Fédération nationale spécifique agricole des cultivateurs de champignons	France	contact@anicc.com	
Bund Deutscher Champignon	Germany	info@der-champignon.de	http://www.der-champignon.de/
CMP – Commercial Mushroom Producers	Ireland	info@mushrooms.ie	http://www.mushrooms.ie/
IFA – Irish Farmers Association	Ireland	info@ifa.ie	http://www.ifa.ie/
CNC Grondstoffen B.V.	The Netherlands	info@cncgrondstoffen.nl	http://www.cnc.nl/
ZLTO –Southern Agriculture and Horticulture Organization	The Netherlands	info@zlt.nl	http://www.zlto.nl
Asociacion Profesional Castellano-Manchega del Champinon y Otros Hongos	Spain	contabilidad@champinter.com	https://web.champinter.com/

¹ Associations have been selected through the European Mushroom Producers Association.

Comestibles

- **Individual producers (conventional and organic):** individual producers, not necessarily linked to associations, are also targeted as a separated audience to assure that all relevant parties within the sector are included in the CD&E plan. Individual producers (part of an association or independent) are the potential early adopters and eventually end users of the BIOSCHAMP solution.
- **Raw material providers:** raw materials providers will be targeted through the dissemination strategy to engage the supply side of the sector with the project, fostering its involvement in future stages. Raw material providers include all agricultural and horticultural producers able to provide agricultural residues/compost to the BIOSCHAMP project. This group includes casing soil providers and biostimulants providers.

5.1.1.1 Actions addressed to this audience group

Actions addressed directly to this group include: BIOSCHAMP practice abstracts (available at EIP-Agri), industry events dedicated to topics of mushroom cultivation (agricultural biostimulants, organic agriculture or bio-based agricultural solutions) and publications in industry magazines.

Table 3: BIOSCHAMP CD&E actions targeted to industry stakeholders.

ACTION	TYPE	TASK	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	KPI No.
Practice abstracts	C	7.4	CTICH	Relevant partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	12
Project website	C&D	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M6	Online	200 views/monthly
Social media	C&D	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online	300 LinkedIn 600 Twitter
Newsletter	C&D		INNOVARUM	CTICH	M6-M42	Online	100
Industry events	D	7.4	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	12
Publications: industry magazines	C&D	7.4	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	7 (together with scientific publications)
Promo materials	C&D	7.4	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	Various targets* ²
Networking	C&D	7.4	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	10 connections
Final event	D	7.4	CTICH	All partners	Project end	Offline	75 attendees

More detail on the actions can be found in point 6 Dissemination and Communication Actions.

² To be addressed in point 6 Dissemination and Communication Actions

5.1.1.2 Message for industry stakeholders

CURRENT SITUATION

Mushroom professional associations and mushroom growers struggle to fight mushroom diseases, one of the most common challenges of mushroom cultivation. There are limited and restricted means to fight the issue, and they are usually focused on an intensive use of pesticides.

Moreover, consumers in Europe are becoming increasingly aware of the extensive use of pesticides in agriculture and developing strong opinions against them, which, ultimately, affects market demand and profitability of the mushroom production.

UTOPIA

BIOSCHAMP provides mushroom producer associations and individual mushroom producers with specific, practical, sustainable, and cost-effective tools to fight mushroom diseases and increase production. A peat-free casing soil enriched with microbiota that reduces the need for pesticides by 90%. BIOSCHAMP reduces the need for chemical inputs, and overall, input costs are reduced.

All in all, the use of the BIOSCHAMP solution (1) boosts the industry profitability by approximately 24% and (2) increases the attractiveness of the final harvested mushroom product to the consumers – who are increasingly aware of the potential dangers of pesticides and fungicides.

5.1.2 Target audience 2: Researchers

Researchers are the key players for knowledge dissemination. Exchange of knowledge and lessons learnt will benefit the research community, facilitating deeper understanding of the specificity of mushroom cultivation and the impact of the BIOSCHAMP solution.

Academic audiences cover:

- **Academic environment.** The academic environment is mainly represented by universities in Europe specialised in agricultural studies or with departments dedicated to the study of these issues as well as by RTOs (Research Technical Organisations)

Within the consortium, the academic environment is represented by Wageningen University & Research (NL) - specialised in strategic and applied research for industry and public institutions, the Department of Plant Sciences of the University of Oxford (UK), with a significant background on microbe-host interactions, Inagro and CSIC (ES).

Then, relevant research organisations that will be targeted outside the consortium include:³

Table 4: relevant research organisations identified

Research Organisation	Country	Contact	Link
AgroParisTech	France	emmanuelle.babsky@agroparistech.fr	http://www2.agroparistech.fr
Aarhus University	Denmark	au@au.dk	https://international.au.dk/
The University of Ljubljana	Slovenia	rektorat@uni-lj.si	http://www.uni-lj.si/eng/
ISARA-Lyon	France	com@isara.fr	http://www.isara.fr/en
Castelo Branco University of Applied Sciences	Portugal	ipcb@ipcb.pt	https://www.ipcb.pt/en/
Estonian University of Life Sciences	Estonia	info@emu.ee	https://www.emu.ee/en
ISA LILLE	France	florence.malaise@yncrea.fr	https://www.isa-lille.com/
University of Santiago de Compostela	Spain		https://www.usc.gal/gl
Polytechnic University of Madrid	Spain	secretaria.vinternacional@upm.es	http://www.upm.es/internacional
Latvia University of Agriculture (LLU)	Latvia	edokuments@llu.lv	https://www.llu.lv/
University College Cork	Ireland	+353 (0)21 490 4734	https://www.ucc.ie/en/
University of Turku	Finland	communications@utu.fi	https://www.utu.fi/en
Linnaeus University	Sweden	info@lnu.se	https://lnu.se/en/
Università Cattolica	Italy		http://www.ucscinternational.it

- **R&D managers.** Technical intensive companies and organisations count with research managers to deliver relevant and updated information to be applied within the organisation. These managers will also

³ Universities have been selected according to EU study recommendations and international standards.

be part of the academic audiences of the BIOSCHAMP project as potential developers of the BIOSCHAMP solution beyond the project time lifespan.

5.1.2.1 Message for academic stakeholders

CURRENT SITUATION

Understanding of the specificity of the mushroom cultivation is limited and the visibility of this field among the vast areas of agricultural studies is reduced. Besides, mechanisms of interaction host and the surrounding microbiota in addition to parasite control through bio stimulants is barely understood.

UTOPIA

There is a deeper understanding of the specificity of mushroom cultivation across the various agricultural academic backgrounds. BIOSCHAMP brings a new perspective, and it is possible to keep on developing new research lines.

BIOSCHAMP supports the development of research about mushrooms, fostering new links and networks among research institutions and RTO

5.1.2.2 Actions addressed to this audience group

Actions addressed directly to this group include publications in peer-reviewed journals and industry magazines and scientific conferences to present technical results of the project.

Table 5: actions addressed to researchers

ACTION	TYPE	TASK	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	KPI No.
Project website	C&D	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M6	Online	200 views/monthly
Social media	C&D	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online	300 LinkedIn, 600 Twitter
Publications in peer reviewed journals	D	7.4	INNOVARUM. CTICH	Academic partners	M1-M42	Online & offline	7 (together with "industrial magazines)
Practice abstracts	C	7.4	CTICH	Relevant partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	12
Promo materials	C&D	7.4	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	(Various targets)
Scientific conferences	C&D	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	3
Networking	C&D	7.4	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	10 connections
Final event	D	7.4	CTICH	All partners	Project end	Offline	75 attendees

5.1.3 Target audience 3: Policy makers

The BIOSCHAMP project will contribute with sector-specific knowledge to the policy topics concerning biostimulants products for mushroom cultivation as well as with measures for peatland protection. Thus, to effectively maximise the impact of this knowledge development, it will be necessary to target specific relevant policy figures among the mushroom sector in Europe. Audiences that with influence over policy for the BIOSCHAMP project include: EU level, national level and regional level stakeholders. This plan has into account that reaching figures with policy influence at EU level is the most challenging level. National and regional policy officers will be easier to reach through partner's contacts and networks.

The CD&E plan of the BIOSCHAMP project will support and the work to be developed by CTICH (project coordinator) and Fertinagro in the Deliverable 6.5 *-Policy recommendations for mushroom biostimulants*, which will work to provide recommendations for adapting the biostimulants regulation to the mushroom sector.

That said, an initial list of relevant policy makers and institutions BIOSCHAMP will target includes:

Table 6: initial list of relevant policy makers for the project

Contact Name	Organisation	Level (EU; national; regional...)	Contact
MAPA	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture	National	
Local Agriculture Departments	National governments	National	
Commission of Agriculture and Rural Development	European Commission	EU	Commissioner: Janusz Wojciechowski
Commission of Agriculture and Rural Development	European Commission	EU	General Director: Wolfgang Burtscher
Committee on European Agricultural and Rural Development	European Parliament	National	Mara Bizzotto – Italy
Committee on European Agricultural and Rural Development	European Parliament	National	Paolo de Castro – Italy
Committee on European Agricultural and Rural Development	European Parliament	National	Jérémy Decerle – France
Committee on European Agricultural and Rural Development	European Parliament	National	Balazs Hidveghi – Hungary
Committee on European Agricultural and Rural Development	European Parliament	National	Jaroslaw Kalinowski – Poland
Committee on European Agricultural and Rural Development	European Parliament	National	Cesar Luena – Spain
Committee on European Agricultural and Rural Development	European Parliament	National	Annie Scherijer-Pierik – Netherlands
Committee on European Agricultural and Rural Development	European Parliament	National	Hilde Vautmans – Belgium
Committee on European Agricultural and Rural Development	European Parliament	National	Maria Walsh- Ireland
EIP-AGRI	European Commission	EU	
European Network for Rural Development (ENRD)	European Commission	EU	

5.1.3.1 Message for policy makers

CURRENT SITUATION

The regulation for biostimulants in Europe is made for plants and may factors do not apply to the cultivated fungi environment.

It is difficult for policy makers to find updated and relevant information about specific crops; thus, it is difficult to develop tailored legislations that address the different producer’s needs.

UTOPIA

BIOSCHAMP delivers tailor made recommendations and suggestions for the registration of biostimulants tailor-made for mushroom cultivation. Policy makers count now with the right tools to develop specific legislation that supports the EU mushroom industry.

5.1.3.2 Actions addressed to this audience group.

Actions addressed directly to this group include: targeted invitations to reach out to experts/ political figures/ authorities on regional, national and EU levels.

Table 7: actions addressed to policy makers

ACTION	TYP E	TAS K	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATIO N	TIMING*	CH.	KPI No.
Project website	C&D	7.5	INNOVARU M	All partners	M6	Online	200 views/monthly
Social media	C&D	7.5	INNOVARU M	All partners	M1-M42	Online	300 LinkedIn, 600 Twitter
Promo materials	C&D	7.4	INNOVARU M	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	(Various targets)
Networkin g	C&D	7.4	INNOVARU M	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	10 connections
Final event	D	7.4	CTICH	All partners	Project end	Offline	75 attendees

5.1.4 Target audience 4: Sustainability Networks

The BIOSCHAMP project will also target networks dedicated to the dissemination of relevant information about sustainability, agriculture, the mushroom sector, nature, climate, or environment in Europe. These networks will be addressed to as “Sustainability Networks”.

“Sustainability Networks” will include organisations like the following:

Table 8: examples of relevant Sustainability Networks

Sustainability Network	Level	Contact	Link
SAI Platform	EU	info@saiplatform.org	https://saiplatform.org/
Growing Media Europe	International	info@growing-media.eu	https://www.growing-media.eu/
Eurosite	EU	info@eurosite.org	https://www.eurosite.org/
Wetlands International	International	post@wetlands.org	https://europe.wetlands.org/
Biorefine Cluster Europe	EU	info@biorefine.eu	https://www.biorefine.eu/
European Regions Research and Innovation Network	EU	info@errin.eu	https://errin.eu/become-member
Solar Impulse Label	EU	fondation@solarimpulse.com	https://solarimpulse.com/label#
European Mushroom Growers Group (GEPC)	EU	contact@anicc.com	http://www.infochampi.eu/
EIP-AGRI	EU		https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en
European Network for Rural Development (ENRD)	EU		https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/

5.1.4.1 Message for the “Sustainable networks

CURRENT SITUATION

Currently, the mushroom sector is underrepresented in networks focused on environment, sustainability, climate change... However, the mushroom industry is highly dependent on pesticides and chemical fungicides –responsible for land deterioration, desertification, and general environmental deterioration.

UTOPIA

BIOSCHAMP actively takes part in networks of projects and organisations that work together to increase the visibility and impact of new innovative solutions that can boost the long-term sustainability of EU resources, supporting measures to fight against climate change, environment degradation due to peat extraction.

5.1.4.2 Actions addressed to this audience group

Actions addressed directly to this group include networking through establishing contact and connections with existing sustainability networks dedicated to topics relevant to the BIOSCHAMP project.

Table 9: actions addressed to the Sustainability Networks

ACTION	TYPE	TASK	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	KPI No.
Project website	C&D	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M6	Online	200 views/monthly
Social media	C&D	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online	300 LinkedIn, 600 Twitter
Promo materials	C&D	7.4	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	(Various targets)
Networking	C&D	7.4	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	10 connections
Final event	D	7.4	CTICH	All partners	Project end	Offline	75 attendees

5.1.5 Target audience 5: General public

The CD&E Plan of the BIOSCHAMP project also considers the importance of reaching a broader spectrum of general audiences not related to the project: citizens, children, students, professional groups not related to the mushroom industry... Increasing awareness within these audience group about the challenges the mushroom industry faces and the solution BIOSCHAMP offers will support the future of the work developed once the project ends as well as its immediate impact.

Ultimately, general audiences will be the final consumers of the product (mushroom) harvested thanks to the BIOSCHAMP solution. Thus, by targeting them the CD&E Plan is supporting final market uptake of the innovation BIOSCHAMP develops, boosting understanding, awareness, and engagement of the final link of the demand side.

5.1.5.1 Message for the general audience

CURRENT SITUATION

The general audiences are not aware of the challenges the mushroom industry faces or about the importance of the need for alternatives to chemical pesticides. Information about the topic is in many cases technical and difficult to access. At the same time, citizens and new generations are increasingly aware of the environmental issues the world is facing and are looking for solutions to support and collaborate.

UTOPIA

BIOSCHAMP works to deliver a sustainable alternative to pesticides for the mushroom industry: a casing soil enriched with microbiota that boosts productivity at lower cost. This results in better and higher quality mushrooms available for all citizens in the EU, produced through a more environmentally friendly approach

5.1.5.2 Actions addressed to this audience group

Actions to be carried out targeted at this audience group include:

Table 10: actions addressed to the general public

ACTION	TYPE	TASK	CD&E LEAD	SUPPORT	TIMING*	CH.	KPI No.
Project website	C	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M6	Online	200 views/monthly
Social media	C	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online	300 LinkedIn, 600 Twitter
Project videos	C	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online	600 views
Press releases	C	7.5	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & offline	5 press releases

6 Dissemination and Communication Actions

6.1 Actions of the CD&E Plan

The Dissemination and Communication Actions that make the strategy of this plan are divided in two groups:

6.1.1 Online channels

Online channels gather actions that will use solely online channels, such as the project website, social media actions and video development and promotion.

Together, these group of actions will help build a strong SEO positioning for the BIOSCHAMP project. Quality internal and external links, social media reputation and curated content will be the base of a solid organic online strategy for the project.

Keywords

Example of keywords to use for SEO positioning and for the creation of Hashtags in the different social media platforms are: BIOSCHAMP, mushroom production, mushroom sector, circular economy, H2020, bioeconomy, sustainability... etc.

6.1.1.1 WEBSITE

A project website is a dynamic portal to the project with all the relevant and key information that the target audiences must know. It is a practical reference tool; all project partners can refer to it in events or in individual meetings. Besides, content can be easily updated and distributed through online means (like mails or social media).

The website is also a great resource of information for all project partners on the last news of the project, changes on dissemination and communication materials, the visual identity of the project and/or on any major event.

By M6 of the project (March 2020), the webpage of the project will be online at: www.bioschamp.eu. The CMS to be used for the webpage will be Wordpress, which offers a wide range of pages, themes, widgets, and plugins.

Responsibility: INNOVARUM is responsible for designing and managing the BIOSCHAMP website.

Table 11: Actions- Website

TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M6-M42	Offline	300 views/month

Notes on abbreviations:

- C: Communication
- D: Dissemination
- D&C: Dissemination and Communication.
- CH: Channel

6.1.1.1.1 Website structure

The structure of the website will be optimised so that user Experience (UX) as well as the User Interface Design (UI) will be both help create a responsible, attractive and easy to access webpage for all targets groups: from those familiar with webpages and technologies to those who might find digital resources a bit more daunting (for example, individual mushroom producers). Some basic pages the website will include are:

- **Home Page.** It will include a summary of the BIOSCHAMP project and objectives.
- **Workplan.** This page will show a description of the work packages (objectives, leading partner, and duration) together with a PERT diagram.
- **Partners.** This page will show a European map locating each partner, including each partner’s brief description.
- **Results dissemination.** This page will contain BIOSCHAMP’s practice abstracts and relevant publications.
- **Videos and media resources.** This page will host dissemination materials such: videos, flyers, and posters.
- **News.** News concerning the project’s development will be published regularly in this section.
- **Contact**

6.1.1.1.2 Partners mention to the BIOSCHAMP project in their webpages

By M6 (March 2020) all project partners will have included a mention to the BIOSCHAMP project in their respective websites. The mention to the project will follow the template provided for all partners in the “Basic DC Guidelines”⁴ provided short after the KOM by Innovarum, which present the project and make acknowledgement of the EU funding.

Table 12: partner’s mention to BIOSCHAMP in their respective webpages

Partner number and short name	Link in website
1 - CTICH	https://ctich.com/bioschamp/
2 - INAGRO	www.inagro.be/Artikel/guid/7061
3 - WR	https://www.wur.nl/en/project/Towards-a-sustainable-peat-free-casing-soil-enriched-with-biostimulants-for-the-mushroom-sector.htm
4 - CSIC	www.irnasa.csic.es/proyectos-vigentes-contaminacion
5 - FERTINAGRO	www.fertinagrobiotech.com/es/noticias/fertinagro-participa-en-el-proyecto-bioschamp-un-sustrato-de-cultivo-bioestimulante-y-alternativo-para-la-industria-del-champinon-en-europa
6 - EKOFUNGI	www.systemekofungi.com/bioschamp/
7 - Innovarum	https://innovarum.es/en/project-portfolio/bioschamp-2/
8 - EUROCHAMP	www.eurochamp.es
9 - KBVB	www.kekkila-bvb.com/kekkila-bvb-is-part-of-the-eu-funded-project-bioschamp/
10 - NEWFOSS	https://newfoss.com/project/bioschamp/
11 - UGLK	https://spgi.pl/en/projects/
12 - UOXF	https://preston.web.ox.ac.uk/home

⁴For more information, got to point 7.3.1 about the “visual identity”.

6.1.1.2 NEWSLETTER

BIOSCHAMP will open a newsletter service targeted to industry stakeholders. The newsletter will be issued annually with any relevant updates for the industry audiences.

Interested audiences will be able to sign up to the newsletter through the project webpage, who will have to provide their business/working email and the name of their organisation (last one, field not compulsory). Finally, the newsletter service will be handled with Mailchimp.

Responsibility: INNOVARUM will run and issue the newsletter with the support of the Project Coordinator (CTICH)

Table 13: Actions- Newsletter

TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
D&C	none	Industry	INNOVARUM	All partners	M6-M42	Online	100

6.1.1.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

The BIOSCHAMP project will open 2 Social Media Accounts for communication purposes: one in Twitter and one in LinkedIn. The CD&E Plan will review in future updates (D7.4) the need of opening new social media accounts in different platforms.

Responsibility: INNOVARUM will be the administrator of all social media accounts that the project opens.

Table 14: Action - Social Media

Action	TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
Social media LinkedIn	C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online	300 Followers
Social Media Twitter	C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online	600 Followers

LinkedIn

LinkedIn counted with 660 million members in 2019, 206 million (31%) of them in Europe.⁵ It is one the platforms with the highest number of EU Funded project accounts and EU Institutions accounts.

LinkedIn is a social platform fully oriented towards professional purposes. It allows the user to create longer posts (around 600 characters per post), to publish articles, photos, and videos. It is also possible to send a request to broadcast live videos to a specific audience. It is especially used for B2B communication purposes with 52% of users between ages 18-49. Besides, more than 70% of users count with higher university studies. Thus, it will be a strong online tool to connect especially with industry audiences (mushroom producers associations), academic audiences, sustainability networks and policy makers.

BIOSCHAMP will count with a “Product Page” linked to the INNOVARUM’s LinkedIn Page. BIOSCHAMP’s logo and identity colours are included in this the LinkedIn product page, together with the EU logo and the acknowledgement to the EU Funding.

Table 15: LinkedIn profile

⁵ LinkedIn Statistics: <https://news.linkedin.com/about-us#statistics>

Twitter

Twitter is also one of the social platforms with the highest number of EU Funded project accounts and EU Institutions accounts. It has a professional focus and B2B communication structure, but it also counts with a wide variety of non-professional profiles. Besides, Twitter allows shorter posts with a maximum of 280 characters and the publication of videos and pictures. This structure makes Twitter one of the main sources of last-minute news and quick updates for the professional and non-professional public. Twitter also allows to broadcast live videos to a specific audience.

63% of Twitter users are between ages 25 and 65 and 57% count with university level studies.⁶ For the reasons above, Twitter will not only be an efficient tool to reach professional audiences (industry, academia, policy makers...), but also general audiences with no scientific/technical background.

BIOSCHAMP will have an independent Twitter account handled by INNOVARUM. BIOSCHAMP's logo and identity colours are included in this the LinkedIn product page, together with the EU logo and the acknowledgement to the EU Funding.

Table 16: Twitter profile

⁶ <https://sproutsocial.com/insights/new-social-media-demographics/#Twitter>

6.1.1.3.1 Initial social media content strategy

The initial steps to build the content strategy of the project include:

1. A series of 10 to 20 posts (adapted for the structure and purposes of each social media channel) with visual content (related images to the text of the post) with different basic messages of the project: check Point 4 of this chapter.
2. These messages can be used to start building awareness on the goals of BIOSCHAMP and on the problems it seeks to solve.
3. Once awareness is built, it is possible to start communicating the activity of the project. The targeted audience (depending on the social media channel) will be more receptive and understand better the materials BIOSCHAMP is providing and talking about.
4. The “Basic Messages” posts can be used again throughout the project. To not be repetitive, it is recommended to pay attention to the programming (making sure that the same message was not posted too soon before) and to make small updates in the messages or the images occasionally.
5. The Basic Messages, together with posts related to the activity of the project partners and the dissemination of the results of the project, will build a solid content strategy.

The Project Social Media accounts will highly benefit from the support of its project partners: bigger institutions with existing online connections and a stronger follower base. INNOVARUM will support all partners’ participation through social media, encouraging them to actively post and mention their respective project actions.

6.1.1.4 VIDEOS

The CD&E Plan of the BIOSCHAMP project envisions the preparation of two videos during the project development:

1. A first, short, animated introductory video of the project to introduce all audiences to the project goals and actions. This video will be launched shortly after the launching of the project website to maximise the actions impact.
2. A longer video that features interviews with all partners closer to the project end. The aim of this second video will be results dissemination.

Responsibility: INNOVARUM is responsible for the production of both videos.

6.1.2 Offline channels and mixed channels

In general, most of the actions will use and benefit from both online and offline channels. That includes press releases, promo materials, publications, and the actions to generate engagement with the “Sustainable Networks” or the policy makers.

6.1.2.1 PROMO MATERIALS

Promo materials cover:

1. Roll ups
2. Flyers
3. Technical infographics

The content of the flyer and, roll-up will be general, informative and will respect the basic colours and visual identity of the project. Fundamental features will be:

- Name, title and logo of the project.
- Project duration (Start and end date)
- GA Number
- EU Funding acknowledgment and EU logo. (KEY)
- Name and location of the project coordinator and of the project partners.
- Contact information: project coordinator and communication partner.
- Project main goals.

Technical infographics will have a more in detail content about the processes the project develops. Thus, INNOVARUM will thoroughly review them together with the Project Coordinator, who will offer technical support.

6.1.2.1.1 The Communication Kit

INNOVARUM will provide all partners with a Communication Kit that includes the promo materials above for all partners to use in events and in other relevant communication actions. The Communication Kit will be provided no later than Month 11 of the project (August 2021).

6.1.2.1.2 Open access

All promo materials will be freely available at the project webpage.

Responsibility: INNOVARUM is responsible for the production of the promo materials. Innovarum will follow up the volume of downloads to track relevance of the materials created.

Table 17: Action - Promo Materials

Action	TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
Roll ups	D&C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	4 designs
Flyers	D&C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	500 prints
Technical infographic	D&C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	100 prints
Downloads total	D&C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	200

6.1.2.2 PRESS RELEASES

Press releases are official statements issued to newspapers/magazines or to other media giving information on a matter, in this, on the BIOSCHAMP project. In total, the project aims to deliver 5 press releases throughout the project implementation: the first one after the Kick Off Meeting (action was completed in October 2020, see Annexes), 3 following the implementation of relevant project milestones, and a last one after the project Final event.

The responsible partner for this action is INNOVARUM. All partners are welcome to do their own press releases as long as they have the approval of the Project Coordinator and include:

1. The mention of the EU-funding.
2. A brief project description and objectives.
3. The consortium composition.

Partners must send a **draft of the publication to Project Coordinator and to the consortium's communication responsible partner 7 days before expected publication**. They will check if the information and attached pictures (if any) can be published. Partners are not in any case allowed to publish their own press releases (as the BIOSCHAMP Project) without the authorisation of the Communication Partner and the Project Coordinator.

Responsibility: INNOVARUM will prepare the project press releases. All partners share the responsibility to send them to the relevant media they have access to.

Table 18: Press releases, KPIs

TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
C	Task 7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	5

6.1.2.2.1 General media coverage

Apart from the project press releases, project partners are encouraged to feature the project in general media channels (TV, newspapers, radio...) whenever possible. Project partners will need to send the article/content to INNOVARUM (Communication partner) before publication for approval.

Besides, partners should also send the published article/link/ content to INNOVARUM for proper communication through the project social media channels as well as for documentation for future reporting.

6.1.2.3 PUBLICATIONS

BIOSCHAMP will actively engage with publications targeted to the industry and academic circles, disseminating the knowledge created, allowing our target groups a deeper understanding of the reasoning of the project.

6.1.2.3.1 Academic publications

BIOSCHAMP will publish in peer-reviewed journals such as:

Table 19: peer reviewed journals examples

Peer reviewed journals	Link	Author Guidelines
Frontiers in Microbiology	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology/author-guidelines
Science of The Total Environment	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/science-of-the-total-environment	https://www.elsevier.com/journals/science-of-the-total-environment/0048-9697/guide-for-authors
Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry	https://pubs.acs.org/journal/jafcau	https://pubs.acs.org/page/jafcau/submission/reference-guidelines.html

Peer reviewed journals	Link	Author Guidelines
PloS One	https://journals.plos.org/plosone/	https://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/submission-guidelines
Chemosphere	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/chemosphere	https://www.elsevier.com/journals/chemosphere/0045-6535/guide-for-authors
Fungal Biology	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/fungal-biology	https://www.elsevier.com/journals/fungal-biology/1878-6146/guide-for-authors
Applied and Environmental Microbiology	https://aem.asm.org/	https://aem.asm.org/sites/default/files/additional-assets/AEM-ITA.pdf

The CD&E Plan of the BIOSCHAMP project also encourages all partners to bring up and select the publications they find most suitable for the project: that is, BIOSCHAMP will also heavily rely on their expertise and experience to write and publish to complete this action.

As a rule, all peer reviewed publications of the BIOSCHAMP project will be open access following the requirements of the European funding program H2020.

6.1.2.3.2 Industry publications

BIOSCHAMP will publish relevant publications for the industry audiences such as:

Table 20: industry magazines examples

Industry magazines	Link	Contact (editor)
Mushroom Business	https://www.mushroombusiness.com/	roel@mushroombusiness.com
Fungimag	https://fungimag.com/	fungimag@gmail.com
The International Society for Mushroom Science	http://www.isms.biz/articles/	
Mushroom news	https://www.americanmushroom.org/main/mushroom-news/	info@americanmushroom.org

Besides, BIOSCHAMP will also make use of the resources available within the project consortium. For example, in this case this includes the Newsletters of ASOCHAMP (ASOCHAMP CTICH) and Inagro (“Champignonberichten”). As in the case with academic publications, BIOSCHAMP will also count on the industry partners expertise and experience to write and publish in relevant magazines to complete this action.

Responsibility: INNOVARUM will oversee and track the development of the publication actions, offering support and advise. All industry and academic partners are expected to carry out at least one publication during the project development: they are the most qualified to develop the content and find a suitable publication platform/magazine/journal.

Table 21: Action - publications

Action	TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
Peer reviewed publications	D	7.4	Researchers	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	7
Industry magazines	D	7.4	Industry	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	

6.1.2.4 PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

Practice abstracts will distribute relevant results of the project in a visual and engaging way, so there is a clear source of information for practitioners and researchers across the EU. BIOSCHAMP will produce and published at least 12 practice abstracts, which will be available both at the project webpage and at the EIP-Agri website.

The practice abstracts will make use of the visual identity of the project when possible, assuring content coherence (Point 7.3.1).

Responsibility: CTICH is responsible for the development of the practice abstracts.

Table 22: Action - Practice abstracts

TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
D	Task 7.4	Researchers & Industry	CTICH	All relevant partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	12

6.1.2.5 EVENTS

The BIOSCHAMP Project will boost its visibility through an active presence in relevant sectorial events. In general, the CD&E Plan of the BIOSCHAMP project encourages all partners to bring up and select the events they wish to participate in with the BIOSCHAMP project. That is, BIOSCHAMP will also heavily rely on their expertise and experience to complete this action.

That said, the Plan also provides a set of general guidelines and recommendations about which events to attend, to assure that the BIOSCHAMP project is visible in the right opportunities. These recommendations cover:

6.1.2.5.1 Industry events

Participation in specialised industry events will enable the project to target stakeholders within the agricultural and mushroom sector, potentially reaching end users. Examples of relevant coming events include:

Table 23: Industry events sample

Industry event	Link	Description	Date	Location
Mushroom Days	https://www.champignondagen.nl/en/welcome/	The international Tradeshow for the Mushroom industry	Not confirmed for 2021	Netherlands
General Meeting of the European Mushroom Grower's Group	http://www.infochamp.eu/	The GEPC is composed of ten European Member States accounting for 90% of the overall European mushroom production	14/07/2021	Online

6.1.2.5.2 Scientific conferences

Participation in scientific conferences will allow the project to deliver presentations of technical results relevant for the scientific environment (researchers). Examples of relevant conferences include:

Table 24: Scientific events sample

Scientific conference	Link	Description	Date	Location
International Society for Mushroom Science Congress	http://www.isms.biz/2021-e-congress/	ISMS will be running a virtual event, ISMS e-Congress 2021.	14-17/09/2021	Online

Biostimulant World Congress	https://informaconnect.com/biostimulants-world-congress/	The Biostimulant World Congress is a celebration of the of latest Biostimulant research.	30/11/2021	Florida
International Conference on Mushroom Biology and Mushroom Products				To be confirmed

Responsibility: INNOVARUM will oversee and track the development of the publication actions, offering support and advise. All industry and academic partners are expected to participate in at least one relevant industry event or scientific conference during the project development: they are also highly qualified to identify relevant events within the sector.

Table 25: Action - Events

Action	TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
Scientific conferences	D	7.4	Reasearchers	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	3
Industry events	D	7.4	Industry	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	12

6.1.2.6 NETWORKING AND THE “SUSTAINABILITY NETWORKS”

BIOSCHAMP will work on networking activities with existing sustainability networks dedicated to topics relevant to the project. BIOSCHAMP will stablish connection with networks and organisations that work on sustainability, environment, agriculture...⁷ through online and offline means. For example, this includes a project section in the network website, collaboration through newsletters or through other type of content exchange or though invitations to events organised by BIOSCHAMP or with the participation of BIOSCHAMP.

BIOSCHAMP will follow and support the contacted “Sustainability Networks” actively through social media and through the best channels available.

Responsibility: Innovarum will lead the contact with relevant networks, however, all partners are expected to contribute whenever possible.

Table 26. Action - Networking

TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
D&C	Task 7.4	Sustainability Networks	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	10

6.1.2.7 INVITATIONS TO POLICY MAKERS

Point 5.1.3 of this document (Audience: policy makers) has stressed the challenge effectively reaching policy makers implies. One of the effective manners to reach out to political figures on regional, national and EU levels is through direct contact. Thus, this plan presents the “Targeted invitations” action, which proposes

⁷ More information about “Sustainability networks” in point 5.1.4 about Sustainability Networks.

sending targeted invitations through written communication or direct contact to identified policy figures within the network of contacts of the project consortium to key events or dissemination actions BIOSCHAMP takes part in. Namely, a key dissemination action will be the Final Event.

BIOSCHAMP will use the initial list of relevant policy makers included in point 5.1.3 Target audience 3: Policy makers and will work through it as the project develops and establishes new connections.

Responsibility: both Innovarum and CTICH will oversee this action. Potentially this action will also require support from FERTINAGRO.

Table 27: Action-Invitations to policy makers

TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
D&C	Task 7.4	Policy makers	INNOVARUM & CTICH	All partners	M1-M42	Online & Offline	12

6.1.2.8 FINAL EVENT

The final event will be organised by the project coordinator (CTICH) in Spain, summarising the outcomes of the project. Key stakeholders from all audience groups will be invited to the event.

Responsibility: CTICH will take care of the organisation of this action. All partners will support and participate in the event.

Table 28: Action-Final Event

TYPE	TASK	AUDIENCE	CD&E LEAD	IMPLEMENTATION	TIMING*	CH.	No.
D&C	Task 7.4	All audiences	CTICH	All partners	M38-M42	Offline	75 attendees

6.2 Contingency actions COVID19

The CD&E Plan of the BIOSCHAMP project has into account that potential contingency actions due to the COVID19 may be necessary. This is also reflected in the “COVID contingency Plan” prepared by the project consortium. Main actions relevant for project communication and dissemination include:

6.2.1 Events

In this regard, actions that could be affected the most are offline events: actions that require person to person contact. For that reason, this plan includes recommendations mostly for online events for 2021.

Additionally, Innovarum will carry out a review looking into 2022, to re-evaluate the event landscape and find opportunities for project promotion. The event landscape has changed dramatically during the last year: many events have been postponed, but many have become online digital versions (both trade show and conference like event). It is to be seen how this situation evolves, it is possible that new event formats become common even after the COVID19 pandemic is completely under control.

6.2.2 Printed materials

It is possible that, due to lack of offline events, the need for printing materials is reduced. If this is finally the case, the Plan will increase the internal target for total downloaded materials from web, increasing actions to maximise its impact.

6.2.3 Final event

This Plan does not still evaluate the potential impact of COVID19 over the Final Event, as the uncertainty level for that case is still too high. Future updates of this Plan will review if any updates will be necessary.

6.3 Measure our progress

6.3.1 Summary of actions and KPIs

The following table summarises all project communication actions and KPIs, and include two columns that include how this project links the audiences groups and actions developed in the Impact section (2.2) of the Grant Agreement and in this CD&E Plan, with the impact indicators to be included in future project reporting in the project section withing the EU Funding and Tenders Portal:

Table 29: summary of actions and KPIs

Action	Type	Task	Target Audience	CD&E Lead	Implementation	Timing	Ch.	KPI	Impact Group (EU F&T Portal)*	Action Equivalent (EU F&T Portal)**
Final event	D&C	7.4	All audiences	CTICH	All partners	M38-M42	Offline	75 attendees	Actions to be reviewed individually	Other/ Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s)/
Project videos	C	7.4	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M6-M42	Online	2 videos	Civil Society	Video/Film
Website	C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M6-M42	Online	300 views/month	General Public	Website
Social media LinkedIn	C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online	300 Followers	General Public	Social Media
Social Media Twitter	C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Online	600 Followers	General Public	Social Media
Roll ups	D&C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	4 designs	General Public	Flyer
Flyers	D&C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	500 prints	General Public	Flyer
Technical infographic	D&C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	100 prints	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Flyer
Download's total (promo materials)	D&C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	200 downloads	Civil Society	Other
Press releases	C	7.5	All audiences	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	5 releases	Media	Press release
Industry magazines	D	7.4	Industry	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	7 publications	Industry	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)

Action	Type	Task	Target Audience	CD&E Lead	Implementation	Timing	Ch.	KPI	Impact Group (EU F&T Portal)*	Action Equivalent (EU F&T Portal)**
Industry events	D	7.4	Industry	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	12 participations	Industry	Exhibition/ Trade Fair/ Brokerage Event/ Pitch Event
Newsletter	D&C	7.5	Industry	INNOVARUM	All partners	M6-M42	Online	100 subscribers	Industry	Other
Invitations to Policy makers	D&C	7.4	Policy makers	INNOVARUM & CTICH	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	12 invitations	Policy Makers	Other
Peer reviewed publications	D	7.4	Researchers	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	7 publications	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Other
Scientific conferences	D	7.4	Researchers	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	3 participations	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Participation to a Conference/ Participation to a Workshop/Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s)
Practice abstracts	D	7.4	Researchers & Industry	CTICH	All relevant partners	M1-M42	Mixed	12 practice abstracts	Actions to be reviewed individually	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)
Networking	D&C	7.4	Sustainability Networks	INNOVARUM	All partners	M1-M42	Mixed	10 connections with sustainability networks	Actions to be reviewed individually	Other

*Impact Groups available in the EU Funding & Tenders Portal include scientific community (higher education, research), industry, civil society, general public, policy makers, media, investors, customers and other.

**Actions in the EU Funding & Tenders Portal include: organisation of a conference, organisation of a workshop, press release, non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication), exhibition, flyer, training, social media, website, communication campaign (e.g. radio, tv), participation to a conference, participation to a workshop, participation to an event other than a conference or a workshop, video/film, brokerage event, pitch event, trade fair, participation in activities organized jointly with other EU project(s) and other

The actions in the project GA foresees for in this Plan do not originally plan activities for the following action indicators in the Funding & Tenders Portal: organisation of a conference, organisation of a workshop, training, communication campaign and participation to an event other than a conference or a workshop. That said, the dissemination plan of the BIOSCHAMP project will be open to adaptation and changes if actions as the listed above were deemed necessary.

To evaluate and keep track of the progress, Innovarum will keep an active communication line with all partners. Additionally, **Innovarum will request all partner to inform of the CD&E actions they have been involved with every 6 months through an easy to fill excel file (Annexes). This file will provide information on the type actions, audience groups involved, and number of people impacted through it.**

6.3.2 Timeline

Table 30: project implementation timeline

Action	Oct-20 M1	Mar-21 M6	Sep-21 M12	Mar-22 M18	Jun-22 M21	Sep-22 M24	Mar-23 M30	Sep-23 M36	Dec-23 M39	Jan-24 M40	Feb-24 M41	Mar-24 M42
Task 7.4: Dissemination activities												
Project website (T7.4)												
Social media Twitter (T7.4)												
Social media LinkedIn (T7.4)												
Publications in peer-reviewed journals and industry magazines (T7.4)												
BIOSCHAMP practice abstracts (T7.4)												
Promo materials: roll ups (T7.4)												
Promo materials: flyers (T7.4)												
Promo materials: technical infographic (T7.4)												
Promo materials downloads total (T7.4)												
Industry events (T7.4)												
Scientific conferences (T7.4)												
Networking: project page in relevant networks websites or through proof of collaboration framework (T7.4)												
Targeted invitations to reach out to experts/ political figures/ authorities on regional, national and EU levels (T7.4)												
Final event organised in Spain (T7.4)												
Task 7.5: Communication activities												
Short video (T7.5)												
Long video (T7.5)												
Press releases (T7.5)												
D7.1 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan												
D7.3 Project website												
D7.4 Update of the D&C actions												
D7.8 Summary of the D&C actions												

7 Partners' obligations regarding CD&E

The following table covers all basic obligations regarding Communication, Dissemination included in the Grant Agreement that all partners must have into account:

Table 31: Dissemination obligations included in the Grant Agreement

ACTIVITY	GRANT AGREEMENT
PROTECTION OF RESULTS – VISIBILITY OF FUNDING	ARTICLE 27 OF THE GRANT AGREEMENT
Applications for protection of results (including patent applications) field by or on behalf a beneficiary must include:	
<i>“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101000651”</i>	
EXPLOTATION OF RESULTS	ARTICLE 28 OF THE GRANT AGREEMENT
If results are incorporated in a standard , the beneficiary concerned must ask the standardisation body to include the following statement in information related to the standard:	
<i>“Results incorporated in this standard received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101000651”</i>	
DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS – OPEN ACCESS – VISIBILITY OF FUNDING	ARTICLE 29 OF THE GRANT AGREEMENT
Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer- reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.	
The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include each of the following mentions:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”. - the name of the action, acronym and grant agreement number - the publication date, length of embargo period if applicable, and - a persistent identifier (DOI). 	
Any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:	
Display the EU emblem. When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have an appropriate prominence. *Please see section use of the EU emblem of the present document	
Include the following text: <i>“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 818312”</i>	
Indicate that it reflects only the author’s view and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.	
PROMOTING THE ACTION – VISIBILITY OF FUNDING	ARTICLE 38 OF THE GRANT AGREEMENT
Any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) or any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded must:	
Display the EU emblem. When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. It is displayed in ANNEX I of the present document.	
Include the following text for communication activities :	
<i>“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation</i>	

programme under Grant Agreement No 101000651”

We hereby show an example of the EU-funding acknowledgement:

And for **infrastructure, equipment and major results**:

“This [infrastructure] [equipment] [insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101000651”

Indicate that it reflects only the author’s view and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

7.1 Communication representative

In order to make the internal communication actions more effective and efficient, each partner will select a “Communication Representative” that will handle all Dissemination and Communication Issues within the organisation. The “Communication Representative” will be the person included in the “Communications mailing list” and will be the person that the Communication Coordinator will contact in case it needs something related to Communication from a partner.

Responsibilities:

1. Be responsible for communication within that entity, acting as the contact person between the entity and the rest of the partners.
2. Ensure that the entity’s communication obligations are fulfilled.
3. Inform the consortium’s communication responsible partner (INNOVARUM, Partner 7) of the communication & dissemination actions carried out by the entity represented, acting as a “speaker” for the wider dissemination of the action.
4. Compile its respective communication activities every 6 months through the Form provided by INNOVARUM (Partner 7).

7.2 Obligations related to notification of Dissemination & Communication Activities

Partners must notify the Communication Partner when:

- They plan **to attend an event**: as soon as possible, ideally no later than 15 days in advance.
- They plan to make a **press release**: minimum 7 days in advance. The Communication Partner (INNOVARUM) must check that the Press Release complies with each of the Grant Agreement obligations. Project partners must wait for the Communication Partner’s (INNOVARUM) or Communication Coordinator’s (CTICH) approval before sending any press release.
- They plan to make any **Scientific Publication** (or general publication: 45 days in advance as per Grant Agreement indications. For more detail, please check Table 31: Dissemination obligations included in the Grant Agreement.
- **Practice abstract**: CTICH (project coordinator) will communicate to Innovarum (Communication Partner) when a practice abstract is ready for open communication and dissemination.

7.3 Harmonising Dissemination and Communication Actions

In order to present a cohesive visual identity of the project, a “Visual Identity Guide” and series of templates for the main dissemination and communication actions have been prepared, so that all documents have the

same format and it makes the information flow easier and unified. The templates were provided by INNOVARUM on M2 of the project (October 2020) to all project partners and cover:

- Template for deliverables
- Template for PowerPoint presentations
- Template for the meetings' agenda
- Template for the meetings' attendance
- Template for the meeting minutes

Partners are expected to follow the indications included in the “Visual Identity Guide” provided in their dissemination and communication actions. In case any project partner has questions about it, it should contact the Communication Coordinator, INNOVARUM.

7.3.1 Visual identity

Main elements of the visual identity of the project include a selection of colours, a font, and the project logo:

Figure 2: project colours

Figure 1: Project font (League Spartan)

- League Spartan

Figure 3: Project logo

The Visual Guide contains information on how and when to use the visual identity, as well as the files so all partners can download, install the fonts and make use of the colours.

8 Knowledge Management, data protection, Open Access, and ethics requirements

Best practices have been defined in order to prevent the disclosure of results susceptible for being protected and included in the Consortium Agreement, which was signed by all the partners.

8.1 Data Management policy

The Data Management policy of the BIOSCHAMP project will be reviewed in the **Data Management Plan** (D7.2, Data Management Plan, WP7), a confidential document which will be developed by the Project Coordinator (CTICH) by Month 6 of the project.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) will outline the principles and processes for data collection, organisation, management, storage, security, analysis and sharing of the project.

8.2 Open access to all findings and publications

Open Access (OA) can be defined as the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the user and that is re-usable. – EU Open Data Portal.

BIOSCHAMP's publication policy will be in line with the Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020.

8.2.1 Practice abstracts & deliverables

Practice abstracts will be self-archived in the BIOSCHAMP website as well as published in the EIP-AGRI website which is also in open access. Deliverables will also be available at the BIOSCHAMP website.

8.2.2 Other online and offline dissemination materials

These include the design of posters, brochures, roll-ups... results or materials produced from workshops, events, or info days as well as any online material distributed through social media or other means.

These types of materials will be openly accessible in the BIOSCHAMP website (D7.2)

8.2.3 Scientific publications

The **Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020**⁸ specifies that open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications (primarily articles) is mandatory:

“Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.” -More detail in Table 31: Dissemination obligations included in the Grant Agreement

⁸Link: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

Thus, all partners will coordinate with the project coordinator and the communication partner (INNOVARUM) the proceedings to assure that the project scientific publications are open access throughout the course of the project.

8.2.3.1 Protocol for open-access publication in the BIOSCHAMP Project (as per the Grant Agreement)

The process for open access publications is the following:

1. Notify the project coordinator and all project partners 45 days in advances of expected publication.
2. As soon as possible, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
3. Ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - On publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher,
 - Within 6 months of publication in any other case.
3. Ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

8.3 Compliance of ethics requirement in CD&E activities

BISOCHAMP will comply with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679 enforced on 25th of May 2018. As a rule, BIOSCHAMP will not collect or process any personal data⁹ in any of its CD&E activities, such as public events, social media (e.g. Twitter, LinkedIn) or webpage content.

Actions in which the BIOSCHAMP project might need to collect and process data include webpage and social media analytics (views, followers, engagement...), the newsletter and networking actions with Sustainability Networks. For the cases above and whenever necessary, BIOSCHAMP will prepare and communicate the GDPR compliant privacy (and cookie policy where applicable) to the data subjects.

If necessary, more details in this regard will be covered in *D9.3: H - Requirement No. 4* of the WP9 Ethics requirements.

⁹ Link: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/what-personal-data_en#:~:text=Personal%20data%20is%20any%20information,person%2C%20also%20constitute%20personal%20dat

Annexes

Image 1: capture of the First Press release of the BIOSCHAMP project

Press Release, Madrid, 01/10/2020

BIOSCHAMP begins, alternative sustainable biostimulant for the European mushroom industry

The mushroom industry plays a key role in the EU's agri-food sector. Nutritionally, it provides a protein-rich alternative to animal products and it is a key source of vitamin D and selenium. Economically, it was valued at €33.7 billion in 2017 and projected to reach €66.8 billion in 2026 (CAGR of +7.9%).

Mushroom cultivation is a highly particular agricultural activity with a unique set of agronomical features and a high sensitivity to several pathogens, which are responsible for major crop losses. Although chemical fungicides (pesticides) have been historically employed, regulatory limitations for mushroom growers and an increasing consumer awareness are urgently requesting solutions to overcome fungicide dependence.

In this context, today a new European project has been launched. **The BIOSCHAMP project aims to develop an integrated approach to tackle the mushroom cultivation challenges: an alternative and sustainable peat-free biostimulant casing for the mushroom industry, reducing the dependency on and need for pesticides and contributing to improve the productivity, the sustainability, and the profitability of the European mushroom sector.** The project will carry out validations at 3 different commercial mushroom farms to ensure the adaptability of the solution in real conditions.

BIOSCHAMP is a 3.5-year international initiative that is starting on 1st of October 2020 and will run until April 2024. **The Mushroom Technological Research Center of La Rioja -Asociación Profesional de Productores de Sustratos y Hongos de La Rioja, Navarra y Aragón- (Spain) (ASOCHAMP-CTICH), will coordinate the implementation of the project.** The project counts with the participation of 12 partners from 6 different countries: CTICH (Project coordinator, ES), Inagro vzw (BE), Stichting Wageningen Research (NL), CSIC (ES), Fertinagro Biotech (ES), Ekofungi (RS), Innovarum (ES), EUROCHAMP (ES), Kekkilä-BVB (NL), NF Fibre B.V. (NL), Uprawa Grzybów Łukasz Kiwała (PL) and University of Oxford (UK). In total, the project gathers 5 Research Technological Centres, 3 large companies and 4 SMEs.

BIOSCHAMP is funded by the EU Commission H2020 Programme under the topic SFS-04-2019-2020 - *Integrated health approaches and alternatives to pesticide use* (Grant Agreement no.: 101000651) and counts with an overall budget of 4.2 million euros.

News and updates on the project will be published on its social media channels: [Twitter @BIOSCHAMP](https://twitter.com/BIOSCHAMP) (<https://twitter.com/BIOSCHAMP>) and [LinkedIn](https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/bioschamp) (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/bioschamp>).

Project details

- Acronym: BIOSCHAMP
- Title: Biostimulant alternative casing for a sustainable and profitable mushroom industry
- Call: H2020-SFS-2020-1
- Project coordinator: CTICH
- 12 partners
- Duration: 3,5 years.
- Budget: 4.2 million euros.
- Link in Cordis: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101000651>

Contact point

Asociación Profesional de Productores de Sustratos y Hongos de La Rioja, Navarra y Aragón (Spain),
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